

Giant Cell Tumor of Distal End of Femur with Pathological Fracture Treated by Resection and Megaprosthesis: A Case Report

DR K. RAGHU NATHA REDDY¹, DR K. VENKATA SUDHAKAR NAIK²,

DR D. LAKSHMI KANTH³, DR. Y.V.SATYANARAYANA⁴

^{3RD} YEAR ORTHOPAEDIC POSTGRADUATE^{1,2,3} ASSISTANT PROFESSOR OF ORTHOPAEDICS⁴
KURNOOL MEDICAL COLLEGE, A P

Abstract:- Giant cell tumor (GCT) is usually a benign tumor of the bone which arises from the metaphysis area and may typically extends into the epiphysis of the long bones. These are neoplasms arising from mesenchymal stromal cells and shows varied manifestations. GCT is considered to be of benign nature but 3% of giant cell tumors of bone are primarily malignant in nature or will undergo malignant transformation and metastasize to lung and other areas. Pathological fracture rates range from 9% to 30% among patients with GCTs of the bone at the time of initial presentation. Due to the lack of definite clinical, radiological, or histological parameters that can accurately predict the progression of the disease, treating this tumour remains a difficult problem. Patients who present with a pathological fracture are frequently thought to have a more aggressive form of disease, which increases their chance of local recurrence and worsens their prognosis. We consider it essential to share a case of a distal femoral GCT with a pathological fracture that was treated by enbloc excision and reconstruction with megaprosthesis with good functional outcome.

Keywords:- GCT, Distal femur, Pathological fracture, Megaprosthesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Giant cell tumour (GCT) is a benign neoplasm of bone which arises primarily from bone and typically involves the epiphysis of long bones. It is one of the commonest tumor that is presented to Orthopaedic surgeon. It accounts for 20% of all benign bone tumours and about 5% of primary bone tumours.¹ It is more prevalent in southern part of India and China, where GCT accounts for 20% of all primary bone tumors². They typically affect patients between the ages of 20 and 40, with a slight female predominance.

The progression of GCT can have a wide range of natural histories, including localised bone destruction, local metastasis, pulmonary metastasis in 3% of patients, metastasis to lymph nodes (rarely), and malignant transformation (rare)^[3-7].

GCT generally has a benign course, but it is known for local recurrence, which has been found to occur between 10% and 50% in various studies. Only 10% of

cases have been known to have undergone malignant transformation.⁸

The most common locations of GCT are the distal femur, proximal tibia, and distal radius, respectively.^{9, 10} Paget disease may be associated with GCT, which most frequently affects the skull, facial bones, pelvis, and spine.¹¹

Majority of the patients with GCT have progressive pain that often is related to activity in initial days and then becomes evident at rest. Unless there has been a pathological fracture, the pain is rarely severe. Pathological fractures range from 9% to 30% among patients with GCTs of the bone at the time of initial presentation.^[12, 13]

Patients who present with a pathological fracture are usually considered to have more aggressive form of disease.¹⁴ Plain radiograph usually shows eccentric radiolucent lytic lesion of epiphysis with thinned out cortex. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is helpful in determining the extent of the lesion within the bone and in the soft tissue. On MRI, the lesion usually appears dark on T1-weighted images and bright on T2-weighted images. MRI also may reveal fluid-fluid levels which is typical of a secondary aneurismal bone cyst, that occurs in 20% of patients. Diagnosis is confirmed by histopathological examination. Grossly, these lesions are chocolate brown, soft, spongy, and friable with blood filled cavities. Microscopically, multinucleated giant cell is seen with background network of stromal mononuclear cells.¹⁵

II. CASE REPORT

This is a case of 26 year old female who presented to opd with pain and swelling of left knee since 1 year which are gradual in onset. Pain was dull aching, non radiating associated with weight bearing on left lower limb without any constitutional symptoms. Patient sustained trivial trauma due to accidental fall after which she was unable to walk and weight bear on that limb. There were no similar complaints in other joints. on examination, patient was conscious, coherent, oriented to time, place and person and vitals are stable. There was 10*8cm solid mass with hard consistency over left distal femur without local rise of temperature. Tenderness and crepitus was present, knee movement restricted and there was no distal neurovascular deficit. Overlying skin was freely mobile without any scar, sinus or dilated veins. Plain radiograph shows expansile lytic lesion involving distal femoral epiphysis and

metaphysis with fracture of distal femur. There was no periosteal reaction. . Patient had her previous xrays of knee which shows initial small, eccentric, radiolucent lytic lesion on lateral aspect of distal femur without any periosteal

reaction and without any fracture, which progressed gradually to involve whole distal femur (predominantly on lateral aspect) with thinned out cortex and surrounding soft tissue involvement which lead to pathological fracture.

Fig. 1: xray showing GCT Left knee

Fig. 2: Xray of GCT with fracture

Fig. 3: CT images –axial, coronal and sagittal cuts

MRI of left knee shows lobulated expansile heterogenous enhancing lesion in metadiaphyseal region and extending to epiphysis of distal end of left femur upto the articular surface without breach in the articular cortex of distal femur. There is associated thinning and break at posterior and lateral aspect of left lateral femoral condyle.

Fig. 4: MRI CORONAL

Fig 5: MRI SAGITTAL

FNAC was done to confirm the diagnosis which showed very few osteoclast type of giant cells with occasional spindle cells in a haemorrhagic background. Computed tomography of the chest, ultrasonography of the abdomen and pelvis were done for

screening of metastasis and there was no evidence of any secondaries. Patient was planned for resection of tumor and insertion of custom made megaprosthesis.

Fig. 6: GCT after dissection

Fig. 7: GCT after resection

Extended medial parapatellar approach was used which helps in vascular dissection and tumor dissection was carried out. The technique of sleeve resection of quadriceps musculature was used which helps in retaining the functioning rectus femoris tendon.

Fig. 8: custom prosthesis after insertion

Fig. 9: MEGAPROSTHESIS

Fig 10: POST OP XRAY

The custom mega prosthesis contains a femoral component, a pivot pin, a thrust-bearing pad which is made up of high molecular weight polyethylene and a tibial component. Proximally, the prosthesis is given 6° lateral angulation to resemble the valgus angulation of the lower limb. The thrust-bearing pad's function is to provide a flexion of 150° between the tibial and femoral components. 3° of rotation is imparted between the femoral and tibial component by the rotating axis mechanism.

Physiotherapy by Quadriceps strengthening exercises was started on 2nd post op day. Weight bearing was allowed with the help of walker on 3rd post op day. On 15th postop day, sutures were removed. Knee bending was started after 3 weeks. At the time of follow-up after 2 months, patient was able to walk without any support with a good range of flexion. There was no evidence of any complication like peri prosthetic infection, flap necrosis or prosthetic failure.

III. DISCUSSION

The management of juxta-articular giant cell tumors around the knee occurring in young patients continues to be one of the most challenging areas in orthopedic oncology¹⁶. Enneking's and Campanacci's radiographic classifications and surgical staging are useful in planning the initial surgical treatment of GCT. Many active (Stage 2) lesions and most of the aggressive (Stage 3) lesions have a higher incidence of local recurrence (20-50%) when treated by curettage with or without bone grafting^{17, 18}. The use of methyl methacrylate cement has equivalent recurrence rates¹⁹. Because of the local aggressive behaviour of GCT and risk of local recurrence, some authors recommend en bloc resection and reconstruction for these Grade III lesions to prevent local recurrence and to preserve the joint²⁰. Although en bloc resection is the treatment of choice for these tumors, wide resection creates a problem for the reconstruction of large bone gaps. The reconstructive procedure has to be based on several considerations, such as durability of the surgical procedure, the oncological prognosis, restoration of the anatomy and function, and the needs of the patient²¹. Rotationplasty gives excellent functional results but the cosmetic outcome after this procedure is a serious disadvantage²². Resection arthrodesis of knee achieves excellent stability but has the major drawback of lack of knee motion²³. After resection of the bone tumor, the use of custom mega prosthesis has become the treatment of choice²⁴. It has become the primary modality of choice for the management of malignant bone tumors in lower limb²⁵. When disease progression has led to clinical situations that prevent skeletal reconstruction following intralesional curettage and in benign aggressive lesions with pathological fractures, custom mega prosthesis has proven to be a simple, technically superior method of replacing the lost segment of bone²⁶. The benefits of a custom mega prosthetic arthroplasty are low recurrence rates, early recovery of knee function, cost effectiveness and unassisted ambulation. The various complications of mega prosthesis include flap necrosis, secondary infection, aseptic loosening and periprosthetic fracture^{27, 28}. Bone resection is not the usual method of choice because of its significant morbidity. It is only indicated in GCT of proximal radius

and distal ulna and fibula, tubular bones of hand and foot, coccyx, sacrum and pelvic bones^{29, 30}. Due to concerns about the therapy's effectiveness and reports mentioning sarcomatous transformation following radiotherapy, radiation therapy is not commonly employed as an adjuvant treatment.³¹ When surgery is not an option or if surgery results in severe disfigurement, radiotherapy might be used as a substitute.³² We did not use any radiotherapy in the treatment of our patients.

IV. CONCLUSION

Distal femur endoprosthetic reconstruction with custom made megaprosthesis was shown to be a safe and reliable technique of reconstructing a large bony defect, created after resection of locally aggressive juxtaarticular tumor with pathological fracture, providing good functional and oncologic outcomes.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Jaffee HL, Lichtenstein L, Portis RB. Giant cell tumor of bone. Its pathologic appearance, grading, supposed variants and treatment. *Arch Pathol* 1940;30:993– 1031.
- [2.] Settakorn J, Lekawanvijit S, Arpornchayanon O, Rangdaeng S, Vanitanakom P, Kongkarnka S *et al*. Spectrum of bone tumors in Chiang Mai University Hospital, Thailand according to WHO classification 2002: A study of 1,001 cases. *J Med Assoc Thai*. 2006; 89:780-7.
- [3.] Campanacci M, Baldini N, Boriani S. Giant-cell tumor of bone. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*. 1987; 69(1):106-14. [Medline].
- [4.] Unni KK. Dahlin's bone tumors: general aspects and data on 11,087 cases. New York, NY. Lippincott-Raven. 1996: 463.
- [5.] Cheng JC, Johnston JO. Giant cell tumor of bone. Prognosis and treatment of pulmonary metastases. *ClinOrthop*. 1997; (338):205-14. [Medline].
- [6.] Connell D, Munk PL, Lee MJ *et al*. Giant cell tumor of bone with selective metastases to mediastinal lymph nodes. *Skeletal Radiol*. 1998; 27(6):341-5. [Medline].
- [7.] Dahlin DC. Caldwell Lecture. Giant cell tumor of bone: highlights of 407 cases. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 1985; 144(5):955-60. [Medline].
- [8.] Grath PJ. Giant-cell tumour of bone: an analysis of fifty-two cases. *J Bone Joint Surg Br*. 1972;54(2):216-29.
- [9.] Murphey MD, Nomikos GC, Flemming DJ, Gannon FH, Temple HT, Kransdorf MJ. Imaging of giant cell tumor and giant cell reparative granuloma of bone: radiologic pathologic correlation. *Radio Graphics*. 2001; 21(5):1283-1309.
- [10.] Turcotte RE, Wunder JS, Isler MH *et al*. Giant cell tumor of long bone: a Canadian Sarcoma Group study. *ClinOrthop Relat Res*, 2002; (397):248-258. CrossRef, Medline
- [11.] Hoch B, Hermann G, Klein MJ, Abdelwahab IF, Springfield D. Giant cell tumor complicating Paget

- disease of long bone. *Skeletal Radiol.* 2007; 36(10): 973-978. Cross Ref, Medline.
- [12.] Dreinhöfer KE, Rydholm A, Bauer HC, Kreicbergs A. Giant-cell tumours with fracture at diagnosis. Curettage and acrylic cementing in ten cases. *J Bone Joint Surg [Br]* 1995;77-B:189–193.
- [13.] Jeys LM, Suneja R, Chami G, et al. Impending fractures in giant cell tumours of the distal femur: incidence and outcome. *Int Orthop* 2006;30:135–138.
- [14.] Dehesi BM, Jaffer SN, Griffin AM, et al. Joint salvage for pathologic fracture of giant cell tumor of the lower extremity. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 2007;459:96–104
- [15.] Werner M. Giant cell tumour of bone: morphological, biological and histogenetical aspects. *Int Orthop.* 2006; 30:484.
- [16.] Vidyadhara S, Rao SK. Techniques in the management of juxta-articular aggressive and recurrent giant cell tumors around the knee. *Eur J Surg Oncol.* 2006.
- [17.] Goldenberg RR, Campbell CJ, Bonfiglio M. Giant-cell tumor of bone. An analysis of two hundred and eighteen cases. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1970; 52:619-64. [PubMed]
- [18.] Larsson SE, Lorentzon R, Boquist L. Giant-cell tumor of bone. A demographic, clinical, and istopathological study of all cases recorded in the Swedish Cancer Registry for the years through 1968. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1975;57:167-73. [PubMed]
- [19.] O'Donnell RJ, Springfield DS, Motwani HK, Ready JE, Gebhardt MC, Mankin HJ. Recurrence of giant-cell tumors of the long bones after curettage and packing with cement. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1994; 76:1827-33. [PubMed]
- [20.] Prosser GH, Baloch KG, Tillman RM, Carter SR, Grimer RJ. Does curettage without adjuvant therapy provide low recurrence rates in giant-cell tumors of bone? *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2005; 435:211-8.[PubMed]
- [21.] Natarajan MV, Annamalai K, Williams S, Selvaraj R, Rajagopal TS. Limb salvage in distal tibial osteosarcoma using a custom mega prosthesis. *Int Orthop.* 2000; 24:282-4. [PubMed]
- [22.] Gottsauner-Wolf F, Kotz R, Knahr K, Kristen H, Ritschl P, Salzer M. Rotationplasty for limb salvage in the treatment of malignant tumors at the knee. A follow-up study of seventy patients. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1991;73:1365-75. [PubMed]
- [23.] Benevenia J, Makley JT, Locke M, Gentili A, Heiner J. Resection arthrodesis of the knee for tumor: Large intercalary allograft and long intramedullary nail technique. *Semin Arthroplasty.* 1994; 5:76-84.[PubMed]
- [24.] Biau D, Faure F, Katsahian S, Jeanrot C, Tomeno B, Anract P. Survival of total knee replacement with a megaprosthesis after bone tumor resection. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2006; 88:1285-93. [PubMed]
- [25.] Malo M, Davis AM, Wunder J, Masri BA, Bell RS, Isler MH *et al.* Functional evaluation in distal femoralendoprosthesis replacement for bone sarcoma. *ClinOrthop Relat Res.* 2001; 389:173-80. [PubMed]
- [26.] Blackley HR, Wunder JS, Davis AM, White LM, Kandel R, Bell RS. Treatment of giant-cell tumors of long bones with curettage and bone-grafting. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1999; 81:811-20. [PubMed]
- [27.] Grimer RJ, Carter SR, Tillman RM, Sneath RS, Walker PS, Unwin PS *et al.* Endoprosthesis replacement of the proximal tibia. *J Bone Joint Surg Br.* 1999; 81:488-94. [PubMed]
- [28.] Yaw KM, Wurtz LD. Resection and reconstruction for bone tumors in the proximal tibia. *Orthop Clin North Am.* 1991; 22:133-48. [PubMed]
- [29.] Doita M, Harada T, Iguchi T, Sumi M, Sha H, Yoshiya S *et al.* Total sacrectomy and reconstruction for sacral tumors. *Spine.* 2003; 28:296-301.
- [30.] Malawar MM, Link MP, Donaldson SS. Sarcomas of bone. *Can Pract Oncol.* 2001; 323:1926.
- [31.] Bell RS, Harwood AR, Goodman SB, Fornasiever VL. Supervoltage radiotherapy in the treatment of difficult giant cell tumors of bone. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 1983;174:208-16.
- [32.] Schwartz LH, Okunieff PG, Rosenberg A, Suit HD. Radiation therapy in the treatment of giant cell tumors. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* 1989; 17:1085-8.